

A NEW APPROACH TO $M(G)$ -GROUP SOFT UNION ACTION AND ITS APPLICATIONS TO $M(G)$ -GROUP THEORY

P.Jeyaraman¹ & R.Nagarajan²

¹Assistant Professor, Department of Mathematics, Bharathiar University, Coimbatore-046.

²Associate Professor, Department of Mathematics, J J College of Engineering & Technology Tiruchirappalli- 620009, Tamilnadu, India

ABSTRACT:

In this paper, we define a new type of $M(G)$ -group action, called $M(G)$ -group soft union(SU) action and $M(G)$ -ideal soft union(SU) action on a soft set. This new concept illustrates how a soft set effects on an $M(G)$ -group in the mean of union and inclusion of sets and its function as bridge among soft set theory, set theory and $M(G)$ -group theory. We also obtain some analog of classical $M(G)$ - group theoretic concepts for $M(G)$ -group SU-action. Finally, we give the application of SU-actions on $M(G)$ -group to $M(G)$ -group theory.

KEYWORDS:

soft set, $M(G)$ -group, $M(G)$ -group SU-action, $M(G)$ -ideal SU-action, soft pre-image, soft anti-image, α -inclusion.

AMS MATHEMATICS SUBJECT CLASSIFICATION: 03E70,08E40,

1.INTRODUCTION:

Soft set theory as in [1, 2, 11, 14, 15, 16, 18, 25, 28] was introduced in 1999 by Molodtsov [22] for dealing with uncertainties and it has gone through remarkably rapid strides in the mean of algebraic structures. Maji et al. [19] presented some definitions on soft sets and based on the analysis of several operations on soft sets Ali et al. [3] introduced several operations Moreover, Atagun and Sezgin [4] defined the concepts of soft sub rings and ideals of a ring, soft subfields of a field and soft sub modules of a module and studied their related properties with respect to soft set operations. Furthermore, soft set relations and functions [5] and soft mappings [21] with many related concepts were discussed. The theory of soft set has also a wide-ranging applications especially in soft decision making as in the following studies: [6, 7, 23, 29] Sezgin et.al [25] introduced a new concept to the literature of N-group called N-group soft intersection action. Operations of soft sets have been studied by some authors, too. of soft sets and Sezgin and Atagun [26] studied on soft set operations as well. In this paper, we define a new type of $M(G)$ -group action on a soft set, which we call $M(G)$ - group soft union action and abbreviate as “ $M(G)$ -group SU action” which is based on the inclusion relation and union of sets. Since $M(G)$ - group
DOI: 10.14810/ijscmc.2017.6101

SU-action gathers soft set theory and set theory and $M(G)$ –group theory, it is useful in improving the soft set theory with respect to $M(G)$ - group structures. Based on this new notion, we then introduce the concepts of $M(G)$ -ideal SU-action and show that if $M(G)$ -group SU-action over U . Moreover, we investigate these notions with respect to soft image, soft pre-image and give their applications to $M(G)$ - group theory.

2.PRELIMINARIES:

In this section, we recall some basic notions relevant to $M(G)$ - groups and soft sets. By a near-ring, we shall mean an algebraic system $(M(G), +, \cdot)$, where

- (N₁) $(M(G), +)$ forms a group (not necessarily abelian)
- (N₂) $(M(G), \cdot)$ forms a semi group and
- (N₃) $(x + y)z = xz + yz$ for all $x, y, z \in G$.

Throughout this paper, $M(G)$ will always denote right near-ring. A normal subgroup H of $M(G)$ is called a left ideal of $M(G)$ if $g(f+i)-gf \in H$ for all $g, f \in M(G)$ and $i \in I$ and denoted by $H \triangleleft_l M(G)$. For a near-ring $M(G)$, the zero-symmetric part of $M(G)$ denoted by $M_0(G)$ is defined by $M_0(G) = \{g \in S / g0=0\}$.

Let G be a group, written additively but not necessarily abelian, and let $M(G)$ be the set $\{ f / f : G \rightarrow G \}$ of all functions from G to G . An addition operation can be defined on $M(G)$; given f, g in $M(G)$, then the mapping $f+g$ from G to G is given by $(f+g)x = f(x) +g(x)$ for x in G . Then $(M(G), +)$ is also group, which is abelian if and only if G is abelian. Taking the composition of mappings as the product, $M(G)$ becomes a near-ring.

Let G be a group. Then, under the operation below;

$$\mu : M(G) \times G \rightarrow G$$

$$(f, a) \rightarrow fa$$

(G, μ) is called $M(G)$ -group. Let $M(G)$ be a near-ring, G_1 and G_2 two $M(G)$ -groups. Then $\phi : G_1 \rightarrow G_2$ is called $M(G)$ - homomorphism if for all $x, y \in G_1$, for all $g \in M(G)$,

- (i) $\Phi(x+y) = \phi(x) + \phi(y)$
- (ii) $\Phi(gx) = g \phi(x)$. It is denoted by G . Clearly $M(G)$ itself is an $M(G)$ -group by natural operations.

For all undefined concepts and notions we refer to (24). From now on, U refers to an initial universe, E is a set of parameters $P(U)$ is the power set of U and $A, B, C \subseteq E$.

2.1.Definition[22]: A pair (F, A) is called a soft set over U , where F is a mapping given by $F : A \rightarrow P(U)$.

In other words, a soft set over U is a parameterized family of subsets of the universe U .

Note that a soft set (F, A) can be denoted by F_A . In this case, when we define more than one soft set in some subsets A, B, C of parameters E , the soft sets will be denoted by F_A, F_B, F_C , respectively. On the other case, when we define more than one soft set in a subset A of the set of

parameters E , the soft sets will be denoted by F_A, G_A, H_A , respectively. For more details, we refer to [11,17,18,26,29,7].

2.2.Definition[6] :The relative complement of the soft set F_A over U is denoted by F_A^r , where $F_A^r : A \rightarrow P(U)$ is a mapping given as $F_A^r(a) = U \setminus F_A(a)$, for all $a \in A$.

2.3.Definition[6]: Let F_A and G_B be two soft sets over U such that $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$. The restricted intersection of F_A and G_B is denoted by $F_A \uplus G_B$, and is defined as $F_A \uplus G_B = (H, C)$, where $C = A \cap B$ and for all $c \in C$, $H(c) = F(c) \cap G(c)$.

2.4.Definition[6]: Let F_A and G_B be two soft sets over U such that $A \cap B \neq \emptyset$. The restricted union of F_A and G_B is denoted by $F_A \cup_R G_B$, and is defined as $F_A \cup_R G_B = (H, C)$, where $C = A \cap B$ and for all $c \in C$, $H(c) = F(c) \cup G(c)$.

2.5 Definition[12]: Let F_A and G_B be soft sets over the common universe U and ψ be a function from A to B . Then we can define the soft set $\psi(F_A)$ over U , where $\psi(F_A) : B \rightarrow P(U)$ is a set valued function defined by $\psi(F_A)(b) = \cup\{F(a) \mid a \in A \text{ and } \psi(a) = b\}$,

if $\psi^{-1}(b) \neq \emptyset$, $= \emptyset$ otherwise for all $b \in B$. Here, $\psi(F_A)$ is called the soft image of F_A under ψ . Moreover we can define a soft set $\psi^{-1}(G_B)$ over U , where $\psi^{-1}(G_B) : A \rightarrow P(U)$ is a set-valued function defined by $\psi^{-1}(G_B)(a) = G(\psi(a))$ for all $a \in A$. Then, $\psi^{-1}(G_B)$ is called the soft pre image (or inverse image) of G_B under ψ .

2.6.Definition[13]: Let F_A and G_B be soft sets over the common universe U and ψ be a function from A to B . Then we can define the soft set $\psi^*(F_A)$ over U , where $\psi^*(F_A) : B \rightarrow P(U)$ is a set-valued function defined by $\psi^*(F_A)(b) = \cap\{F(a) \mid a \in A \text{ and } \psi(a) = b\}$, if $\psi^{-1}(b) \neq \emptyset$,

$= \emptyset$ otherwise for all $b \in B$. Here, $\psi^*(F_A)$ is called the soft anti image of F_A under ψ .

2.7 Definition [8]: Let f_A be a soft set over U and α be a subset of U . Then, lower α -inclusion of a soft set f_A , denoted by f_A^α , is defined as $f_A^\alpha = \{x \in A : f_A(x) \subseteq \alpha\}$

3. M(G) –GROUP SU-ACTION

In this section, we first define $M(G)$ -group soft union action, abbreviated as $M(G)$ -group SU-action with illustrative examples. We then study their basic results with respect to soft set operation.

3.1Definition: Let S be an $M(G)$ - group and f_S be a fuzzy soft set over U , then f_S is called fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ - group over U if it satisfies the following conditions;

$$(FS_{UN-1}) f_S(x+y) \subseteq f_S(x) \cup f_S(y)$$

$$(FS_{UN-2}) f_S(-x) \subseteq f_S(x)$$

$$(FS_{UN-3}) f_S(gx) \subseteq f_S(x)$$

For all $x, y \in S$ and $g \in M(G)$.

3.1Example: Consider the near-ring module $M(G) = \{e, f, g, h\}$, be the near-ring under the operation defined by the following table:

+	e	f	g	h
e	e	f	g	h
f	f	e	f+g	f+h
g	g	g+h	e	g+h
h	h	h+f	h+g	e

.	e	f	g	h
0	e	f	g	h
f	f	e	f•g	f•h
g	g	g•h	e	g•h
h	h	h•f	h•g	e

Let $G=M(G)$ be the set of functions and

and $U = \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} f & e \\ f & e \end{bmatrix} / f, e \in M(G) \right\}$, 2×2 matrices with four terms, is the universal set. we construct a soft set.

$$f_s(e) = \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} e & 0 \\ e & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\}, \quad f_s(f) = f_s(g) = f_s(h) = \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} f & 0 \\ f & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} g & 0 \\ g & 0 \end{bmatrix}, \begin{bmatrix} 3 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\}$$

Then one can easily show that the soft set f_s is a $M(G)$ -group SU-action over U .

3.1 Proposition: Let f_s be a fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ - group over U . Then, $f_s(0) \subseteq f_s(x)$ for all $x \in S$.

Proof: Assume that f_s is fuzzy SU-action over U . Then, for all $x \in S$, $f_s(0) = f_s(x-x) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(-x) = f_s(x) \cup f_s(x) = f_s(x)$.

3.1 Theorem: Let S be a fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ - group and f_s be a fuzzy soft set over U . Then f_s is SU-action of $M(G)$ - group over U if and only if

- (i) $f_s(x-y) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(y)$
- (ii) $f_s(gx) \subseteq f_s(x)$ for all $x, y \in S$ and $g \in M(G)$.

Proof: Suppose f_s is a fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ - group over U . Then, by definition-3.1, $f_s(xy) \subseteq f_s(y)$ and $f_s(x-y) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(-y) = f_s(x) \cup f_s(y)$ for all $x, y \in S$

Conversely, assume that $f_s(xy) \subseteq f_s(y)$ and $f_s(x-y) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(y)$ for all $x, y \in S$.

If we choose $x=0$, then $f_s(0-y) = f_s(-y) \subseteq f_s(0) \cup f_s(y) = f_s(y)$ by proposition-3.1. Similarly

$f_s(y) = f_s(-(-y)) \subseteq f_s(-y)$, thus $f_s(-y) = f_s(y)$ for all $y \in S$. Also, by assumption $f_s(x-y) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(-y) = f_s(x) \cup f_s(y)$. This complete the proof.

3.2Theorem: Let f_s be a fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ - group over U .

- (i) If $f_s(x-y) = f_s(0)$ for any $x, y \in S$, then $f_s(x) = f_s(y)$.
- (ii) $f_s(x-y) = f_s(0)$ for any $x, y \in S$, then $f_s(x) = f_s(y)$.

Proof: Assume that $f_s(x-y) = f_s(0)$ for any $x, y \in S$, then

$$\begin{aligned} f_s(x) &= f_s(x-y+y) \subseteq f_s(x-y) \cup f_s(y) \\ &= f_s(0) \cup f_s(y) = f_s(y) \end{aligned}$$

and similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} f_s(y) &= f_s((y-x)+x) \subseteq f_s(y-x) \cup f_s(x) \\ &= f_s(-(y-x)) \cup f_s(x) \\ &= f_s(0) \cup f_s(x) = f_s(x) \end{aligned}$$

Thus, $f_s(x) = f_s(y)$ which completes the proof. Similarly, we can show the result (ii).

It is known that if S is an $M(G)$ -group, then $(S, +)$ is a group but not necessarily abelian.

That is, for any $x, y \in S$, $x+y$ needs not be equal to $y+x$. However, we have the following:

3.3 Theorem: Let f_s be fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ -group over U and $x \in S$. Then,

$$f_s(x) = f_s(0) \Leftrightarrow f_s(x+y) = f_s(y+x) = f_s(y) \text{ for all } y \in S.$$

Proof: Suppose that $f_s(x+y) = f_s(y+x) = f_s(y)$ for all $y \in S$. Then, by choosing $y = 0$, we obtain that $f_s(x) = f_s(0)$.

Conversely, assume that $f_s(x) = f_s(0)$. Then by proposition-3.1, we have $f_s(0) = f_s(x) \subseteq f_s(y)$, $\forall y \in S$ (1)

Since f_s is fuzzy SU-action on N -module over U , then

$$\begin{aligned} f_s(x+y) &\subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(y) = f_s(y), \forall y \in S. \text{ Moreover, for all } y \in S \\ f_s(y) &= f_s((-x)+x+y) = f_s(-x+(x+y)) \subseteq f_s(-x) \cup f_s(x+y) \\ &= f_s(x) \cup f_s(x+y) = f_s(x+y) \end{aligned}$$

Since by equation (1), $f_s(x) \subseteq f_s(y)$ for all $y \in S$ and $x, y \in S$, implies that $x+y \in S$. Thus, it follows that $f_s(x) \subseteq f_s(x+y)$. So $f_s(x+y) = f_s(y)$ for all $y \in S$.

Now, let $x \in S$. Then, for all $x, y \in S$

$$\begin{aligned} f_s(y+x) &= f_s(y+x+(y-y)) \\ &= f_s(y+(x+y)-y) \\ &\subseteq f_s(y) \cup f_s(x+y) \cup f_s(y) \\ &= f_s(y) \cup f_s(x+y) = f_s(y) \end{aligned}$$

Since $f_s(x+y) = f_s(y)$. Furthermore, for all $y \in S$

$$\begin{aligned} f_s(y) &= f_s(y+(x-x)) \\ &= f_s((y+x)-x) \\ &\subseteq f_s(y+x) \cup f_s(x) \\ &= f_s(y+x) \text{ by equation(1).} \end{aligned}$$

It follows that $f_s(y+x) = f_s(y)$ and so $f_s(x+y) = f_s(y+x) = f_s(y)$, for all $y \in S$, which completes the proof.

3.4 Theorem: Let S be a near-field and f_s be a fuzzy soft set over U . If $f_s(0) \subseteq f_s(1) = f_s(x)$ for all $0 \neq x \in S$, then it is fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ -group over U .

Proof: Suppose that $f_S(0) \subseteq f_S(1) = f_S(x)$ for all $0 \neq x \in S$. In order to prove that it is fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ - group over U , it is enough to prove that $f_S(x-y) \subseteq f_S(x) \cup f_S(y)$ and $f_S(gx) \subseteq f_S(x)$.

Let $x, y \in S$. Then we have the following cases:

Case-1: Suppose that $x \neq 0$ and $y=0$ or $x=0$ and $y \neq 0$. Since S is a near-field, so it follows that $gx=0$ and $f_S(gx) = f_S(0)$. since $f_S(0) \subseteq f_S(x)$, for all $x \in S$, so $f_S(nx) = f_S(0) \subseteq f_S(x)$, and $f_S(nx) = f_S(0) \subseteq f_S(y)$. This imply $f_S(gx) \subseteq f_S(x)$.

Case-2: Suppose that $x \neq 0$ and $y \neq 0$. It follows that $nx \neq 0$. Then, $f_S(nx) = f_S(1) = f_S(x)$ and $f_S(gx) = f_S(1) = f_S(y)$, which implies that $f_S(gx) \subseteq f_S(x)$.

Case-3: suppose that $x=0$ and $y=0$, then clearly $f_S(gx) \subseteq f_S(x)$. Hence $f_S(gx) \subseteq f_S(x)$, for all $x, y \in S$.

Now, let $x, y \in S$. Then $x-y=0$ or $x-y \neq 0$. If $x-y=0$, then either $x=y=0$ or $x \neq 0, y \neq 0$ and $x=y$. But, since $f_S(x-y) = f_S(0) \subseteq f_S(x)$, for all $x \in S$, it follows that $f_S(x-y) = f_S(0) \subseteq f_S(x) \cup f_S(y)$. If $x-y \neq 0$, then either $x \neq 0, y \neq 0$ and $x \neq y$ or $x \neq 0$ and $y=0$ or $x=0$ and $y \neq 0$.

Assume that $x \neq 0, y \neq 0$ and $x \neq y$. This follows that

$$f_S(x-y) = f_S(1) = f_S(x) \subseteq f_S(x) \cup f_S(y).$$

Now, let $x \neq 0$ and $y=0$. Then $f_S(x-y) \subseteq f_S(x) \cup f_S(y)$. Finally, let $x=0$ and $y \neq 0$. Then, $f_S(x-y) \subseteq f_S(x) \cup f_S(y)$. Hence $f_S(x-y) \subseteq f_S(x) \cup f_S(y)$, for all $x, y \in S$. Thus, f_S is fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ - group over U .

3.5 Theorem: Let f_S and f_T be two fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ - group over U . Then $f_S \wedge f_T$ is fuzzy soft SU-action on $M(G)$ - group over U .

Proof: let $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2) \in S \times T$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} f_{S \wedge T} \left((x_1, y_1) - (x_2, y_2) \right) &= f_{S \wedge T} (x_1 - x_2, y_1 - y_2) \\ &= f_S (x_1 - x_2) \cap f_T (y_1 - y_2) \\ &\subseteq (f_S (x_1) \cup f_S (x_2)) \cap (f_T (y_1) \cup f_T (y_2)) \\ &= (f_S (x_1) \cup f_T (y_1)) \cap (f_S (x_2) \cup f_T (y_2)) \\ &= f_{S \wedge T} (x_1, y_1) \cap f_{S \wedge T} (x_2, y_2) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} f_{S \wedge T} \left((g_1, g_2), (x_2, y_2) \right) &= f_{S \wedge T} (n_1 x_2, n_2 y_2) \\ &= f_S (g_1 x_2) \cap f_T (g_2 y_2) \\ &\subseteq f_S (x_2) \cap f_T (y_2) \\ &= f_{S \wedge T} (x_2, y_2) \end{aligned}$$

Thus $f_S \wedge f_T$ is fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ - group over U .

Note that $f_S \vee f_T$ is not fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ - group over U .

3.2Example: Assume $U = p_3$ is the universal set. Let $S = Z_3$ and $H = \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} a & a \\ b & b \end{bmatrix} / a, b \in Z_3 \right\}$ 2×2 matrices with Z_3 terms, be set of parameters. We define fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ - group f_S over $U = p_3$ by

$$\begin{aligned} f_S(0) &= p_3 \\ f_S(1) &= \{(1), (1\ 2), (1\ 3\ 2)\} \\ f_S(2) &= \{(1), (1\ 2), (1\ 2\ 3), (1\ 3\ 2)\} \end{aligned}$$

We define fuzzy SU-action on N -module f_H over $U = p_3$ by

$$\begin{aligned} f_H \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \right\} &= p_3 \\ f_H \left\{ \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \right\} &= \{(1), (1\ 2), (1\ 3\ 2)\} \end{aligned}$$

Then $f_S \vee f_T$ is not fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ - group over U .

3.2Definition: Let f_S, g_T be fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ - group over U . Then product of fuzzy

SU-action on $M(G)$ - group f_S and g_T is defined as $f_S \times g_T = h_{S \times T}$, where $h_{S \times T}(x, y) = f_S(x) \times g_T(y)$ for all $(x, y) \in S \times T$.

3.6Theorem: If f_S and g_T are fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ - group over U . Then so is $f_S \times g_T$ over $U \times U$.

Proof: By definition-3.2, let $f_S \times g_T = h_{S \times T}$, where $h_{S \times T}(x, y) = f_S(x) \times g_T(y)$ for all $(x, y) \in S \times T$. Then for all $(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2) \in S \times T$ and $(n_1, n_2) = N \times N$.

$$\begin{aligned} h_{S \times T} \left((x_1, y_1) - (x_2, y_2) \right) &= h_{S \times T} (x_1 - x_2, y_1 - y_2) \\ &= f_S(x_1 - x_2) \times g_T(y_1 - y_2) \\ &\subseteq (f_S(x_1) \cup f_S(x_2)) \times (g_T(y_1) \cup g_T(y_2)) \\ &= (f_S(x_1) \times g_T(y_1)) \cup (f_S(x_2) \times g_T(y_2)) \\ &= h_{S \times T}(x_1, y_1) \cup h_{S \times T}(x_2, y_2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} h_{S \times T} \left((g_1, g_2)(x_2, y_2) \right) &= h_{S \times T}(n_1 x_2, n_2 y_2) \\ &= f_S(g_1 x_2) \times g_T(g_2 y_2) \\ &\subseteq f_S(x_2) \times g_T(y_2) \\ &= h_{S \times T}(x_2, y_2) \end{aligned}$$

Hence $f_S \times g_T = h_{S \times T}$ is fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ - group over U .

3.7Theorem: If f_S and h_S are fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ -group over U , then so is $f_S \tilde{\cap} h_S$ over U .

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Let } x, y \in s \text{ and } n \in N \text{ then} \\ (f_S \tilde{\cap} h_S)(x-y) &= f_S(x-y) \cap h_S(x-y) \\ &\subseteq (f_S(x) \cup f_S(y)) \cap (h_S(x) \cup h_S(y)) \\ &= (f_S(x) \cap h_S(x)) \cup (f_S(y) \cap h_S(y)) \\ &= (f_S \tilde{\cap} h_S)(x) \cup (f_S \tilde{\cap} h_S)(y) \end{aligned}$$

$(f_S \tilde{\cap} h_S)(nx) = f_S(nx) \cap h_S(nx) \subseteq f_S(x) \cap h_S(x) = (f_S \tilde{\cap} h_S)(x)$
 Therefore, $(f_S \tilde{\cap} h_S)$ is fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ -group over U .

4.SU-ACTION ON $M(G)$ -IDEAL STRUCTURES

4.1 Definition : Let S be an $M(G)$ -group and f_S be a fuzzy soft set over U . Then f_S is called fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ -ideal of S over U if the following conditions are satisfied:

- (i) $f_S(x + y) \subseteq f_S(x) \cup f_S(y)$
- (ii) $f_S(-x) = f_S(x)$
- (iii) $f_S(x + y - x) \subseteq f_S(y)$
- (iv) $f_S(g(x + y) - gx) \subseteq f_S(y)$ for all $x, y \in S$ and $g \in M(G)$.

Here, note that

$$f_S(x + y) \subseteq f_S(x) \cup f_S(y) \text{ and } f_S(-x) = f_S(x) \text{ imply } f_S(x - y) \subseteq f_S(x) \cup f_S(y)$$

4.1Example: Consider $M(G) = \{0, x, y, z\}$ with the following tables

+	0	x	y	z
0	0	x	y	z
x	x	0	z	y
y	y	z	0	x
z	z	y	x	0

.	0	x	y	z
0	0	0	0	0
x	0	0	0	x
y	0	x	y	y
z	0	x	y	z

Let $S=M(G)$ be the parameters and $U= D_2$, dihedral group, be the universal set. We define a fuzzy soft set f_S over U by $f_S(0) = D_2$, $f_S(x) = \{e, b, ba\}$, $f_S(y) = \{a, b\}$, $f_S(z) = \{b\}$. Then, one can show that f_S is fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ -ideal of S over U .

4.2 Example: Consider the near $-$ ring $N=\{0,1,2,3\}$ with the following tables

+	0	1	2	3
0	0	1	2	3
1	1	2	3	0
2	2	3	0	1
3	3	0	1	2

.	0	x	y	z
0	0	0	0	0
x	0	1	0	1
y	0	3	0	3
z	0	2	0	2

Let $S=M(G)$ be the set of parameters and $U= Z^+$ be the universal set. We define a fuzzy soft set

$$f_S \text{ over } U \text{ by } f_S(0) = \{ 1, 2, 3, 5, 6, 7, 9, 10, 11, 17 \}$$

$$f_S(1) = f_S(3) = \{ 1, 3, 5, 7, 9, 11 \}, f_S(2) = \{ 1, 5, 7, 9, 11 \}$$

Since $f_s(2.(3 + 1) - 2.3) = f_s(2.1 - 2.3) = f_s(3 - 3) = f_s(0) \not\subseteq f_s(1)$

Therefore, f_s is not fuzzy SU-action on M(G)-ideal over U. It is known that if M(G) is a zero-symmetric near-ring, then every M(G)-ideal of S is also M(G)-group of S. Here, we have an analog for this case.

4.1 Theorem: Let M(G) be a zero-symmetric near-ring. Then, every fuzzy SU-action on M(G)-ideal is fuzzy SU-action on M(G)-group over U.

Proof: Let f_s be a fuzzy SU-action on M(G)-ideal on S over U. Since $f_s(g(x+y)-gx) \subseteq f_s(y)$, for all $x, y \in S$, and $g \in M(G)$, in particular for $x=0$, it follows that $f_s(g(0+y)-g.0) = f_s(ny-0) = f_s(y) \subseteq f_s(y)$. Since the other condition is satisfied by definition-4.1, f_s is fuzzy SU-action on M(G)-ideals of S over U.

4.2 Theorem: Let f_s be fuzzy SU-action on M(G)-ideal of S and f_T be fuzzy SU-action on M(G)-ideal of T over U. Then $f_s \wedge f_T$ is fuzzy SU-action on M(G)-ideal of $S \times T$ over U.

4.3 Theorem : If f_s is fuzzy SU-action on M(G)-ideal of S and f_T be fuzzy SU-action on M(G)-ideal of T over U, then $f_s \times f_T$ is fuzzy SU-action on M(G)-ideal over $U \times U$.

4.4 Theorem : If f_s and h_s are two fuzzy SU-action on M(G)-group of S over U, then $f_s \tilde{\cap} h_s$ is Fuzzy SU-action on M(G)-ideal over U.

5.APPLICATION OF FUZZY SU-ACTION ON M(G)- GROUP

In this section, we give the applications of fuzzy soft image, soft pre-image, lower α -inclusion of fuzzy soft sets and M(G)-group homomorphism with respect to fuzzy SU-action on M(G)-group and M(G)-ideal.

5.1 Theorem: If f_s is fuzzy SU-action on M(G)-ideal of S over U, then $S^f = \{x \in S / f_s(x) = f_s(0)\}$ is a M(G)-ideal of S.

Proof: It is obvious that $0 \in S^f$ we need to show that (i) $x-y \in S^f$, (ii) $s+x-s \in S^f$ and (iii) $g(s+x)-gs \in S^f$ for all $x, y \in S^f$ and $g \in M(G)$ and $s \in S$.

If $x, y \in S^f$, then $f_s(x) = f_s(y) = f_s(0)$. By proposition-3.1, $f_s(0) \subseteq f_s(x-y)$, $f_s(0) \subseteq f_s(s+x-s)$, and $f_s(0) \subseteq f_s(g(s+x)-gs)$ for all $x, y \in S^f$ and $g \in M(G)$ and $s \in S$. Since f_s is fuzzy SU-action on M(G)-ideal of S over U, then for all $x, y \in S^f$ and $g \in M(G)$ and $s \in S$.

- (i) $f_s(x-y) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(y) = f_s(0)$.
- (ii) $f_s(s+x-s) \subseteq f_s(x) = f_s(0)$.
- (iii) $f_s(g(s+x)-gs) \subseteq f_s(x) = f_s(0)$.

Hence $f_s(x-y) = f_s(0)$, $f_s(s+x-s) = f_s(0)$ and $f_s(g(s+x)-gs) = f_s(0)$, for all $x, y \in S^f$ and $g \in M(G)$ and $s \in S$. Therefore S^f is M(G)-ideal of S.

5.2 Theorem: Let f_s be fuzzy soft set over U and α be a subset of U such that $\emptyset \ni \alpha \ni f_s(0)$. If f_s is fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ -ideal over U , then $f_s^{\subseteq \alpha}$ is an $M(G)$ -ideal of S .

Proof: Since $f_s(0) \subseteq \alpha$, then $0 \in f_s^{\subseteq \alpha}$ and $\emptyset \neq f_s^{\subseteq \alpha} \ni S$. Let $x, y \in f_s^{\subseteq \alpha}$, then $f_s(x) \subseteq \alpha$ and $f_s(y) \subseteq \alpha$. We need to show that

- (i) $x-y \in f_s^{\subseteq \alpha}$
- (ii) $s+x-s \in f_s^{\subseteq \alpha}$
- (iii) $g(s+x)-ns \in f_s^{\subseteq \alpha}$ for all $x, y \in f_s^{\subseteq \alpha}$ and $g \in M(G)$ and $s \in S$.

Since f_s is fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ -ideal over U , it follows that

- (i) $f_s(x-y) \subseteq f_s(x) \cup f_s(y) \subseteq \alpha \cup \alpha = \alpha$,
- (ii) $f_s(s+x-s) \subseteq f_s(x) \subseteq \alpha$ and
- (iii) $f_s(g(s+x)-gs) \subseteq f_s(x) \subseteq \alpha$. Thus, the proof is completed.

5.3 Theorem : Let f_s and f_T be fuzzy soft sets over U and χ be an $M(G)$ -isomorphism from S to T . If f_s is fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ -ideal of S over U , then $\chi(f_s)$ is fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ -ideal of T over U .

Proof: Let δ_1, δ_2 and $g \in M(G)$. Since χ is surjective, there exists $s_1, s_2 \in S$ such that $\chi(s_1) = \delta_1$ and $\chi(s_2) = \delta_2$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (\chi f_s) (\delta_1 - \delta_2) &= \cup \{ f_s(s) / s \in S, \chi(s) = \delta_1 - \delta_2 \} \\ &= \cup \{ f_s(s) / s \in S, s = \chi^{-1}(\delta_1 - \delta_2) \} \\ &= \cup \{ f_s(s) / s \in S, s = \chi^{-1}(\chi(s_1 - s_2)) = s_1 - s_2 \} \\ &= \cup \{ f_s(s_1 - s_2) / s_i \in S, \chi(s_i) = \delta_i, i = 1, 2, \dots \} \\ &\subseteq \cup \{ f_s(s_1) \cup f_s(s_2) / s_i \in S, \chi(s_i) = \delta_i, i = 1, 2, \dots \} \\ &= (\cup \{ f_s(s_1) / s_1 \in S, \chi(s_1) = \delta_1 \}) \cup (\cup \{ f_s(s_2) / s_2 \in S, \chi(s_2) = \delta_2 \}) \\ &= (\chi f_s) (\delta_1) \cup (\chi f_s) (\delta_2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Also } (\chi f_s) (\delta_1 + \delta_2 - \delta_1) &= \cup \{ f_s(s) / s \in S, \chi(s) = \delta_1 + \delta_2 - \delta_1 \} \\ &= \cup \{ f_s(s) / s \in S, s = \chi^{-1}(\delta_1 + \delta_2 - \delta_1) \} \\ &= \cup \{ f_s(s) / s \in S, s = \chi^{-1}(\chi(s_1 + s_2 - s_1)) = s_1 + s_2 - s_1 \} \\ &= \cup \{ f_s(s_1 + s_2 - s_1) / s_i \in S, \chi(s_i) = \delta_i, i = 1, 2, \dots \} \\ &\subseteq \cup \{ f_s(s_2) / s_2 \in S, \chi(s_2) = \delta_2 \} \\ &= (\chi f_s) (\delta_2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Furthermore, } (\chi f_s) (g(\delta_1 + \delta_2) - g\delta_1) &= \cup \{ f_s(s) / s \in S, \chi(s) = g(\delta_1 + \delta_2) - g\delta_1 \} \\ &= \cup \{ f_s(s) / s \in S, s = \chi^{-1}(g(\delta_1 + \delta_2) - g\delta_1) \} \\ &= \cup \{ f_s(s) / s \in S, s = g(s_1 + s_2) - g s_1 \} \\ &= \cup \{ f_s(g + s_2) - g s_1 / s_i \in S, \chi(s_i) = \delta_i, i = 1, 2, \dots \} \\ &\subseteq \cup \{ f_s(s_2) / s_2 \in S, \chi(s_2) = \delta_2 \} \\ &= (\chi f_s) (\delta_2). \end{aligned}$$

Hence $\chi(f_s)$ is fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ -ideal of T over U .

5.4Theorem: Let f_S and f_T be fuzzy soft sets over U and χ be an $M(G)$ -isomorphism from S to T . If f_T is fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ -ideal of T over U , then $\chi^{-1}(f_T)$ is fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ -ideal of S over U .

Proof: Let $s_1, s_2 \in S$ and $g \in M(G)$. Then

$$\begin{aligned} (\chi^{-1}(f_T))(s_1 - s_2) &= f_T(\chi(s_1 - s_2)) \\ &= f_T(\chi(s_1) - \chi(s_2)) \\ &\subseteq f_T(\chi(s_1)) \cup f_T(\chi(s_2)) \\ &= (\chi^{-1}(f_T))(s_1) \cup (\chi^{-1}(f_T))(s_2). \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Also } (\chi^{-1}(f_T))(s_1 + s_2 - s_1) &= f_T(\chi(s_1 + s_2 - s_1)) \\ &= f_T(\chi(s_1) + \chi(s_2) - \chi(s_1)) \\ &\subseteq f_T(\chi(s_2)) = (\chi^{-1}(f_T))(s_2) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Furthermore, } (\chi^{-1}(f_T))(g(s_1 + s_2) - gs_1) &= f_T(\chi(g(s_1 + s_2) - gs_1)) \\ &= f_T(g(\chi(s_1) + \chi(s_2)) - g\chi(s_1)) \\ &\subseteq f_T(\chi(s_2)) = (\chi^{-1}(f_T))(s_2) \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $(\chi^{-1}(f_T))$ is fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ -ideal of S over U .

CONCLUSION:

In this paper, we have defined a new type of N -module action on a fuzzy soft set, called fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ -group by using the soft sets. This new concept picks up the soft set theory, fuzzy theory and $M(G)$ -group theory together and therefore, it is very functional for obtaining results in the mean of $M(G)$ -group structure. Based on this definition, we have introduced the concept of fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ -ideal. We have investigated these notions with respect to soft image, soft pre-image and lower α -inclusion of soft sets. Finally, we give some application of fuzzy SU-action on $M(G)$ -ideal to $M(G)$ -group theory. To extend this study, one can further study the other algebraic structures such as different algebra in view of their SU-actions.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT:

The authors are highly grateful to the referees for their valuable comments and suggestions for improving papers.

REFERENCES

- [1] Acar U., Koyuncu F., Tanay B., Soft sets and soft rings, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 59(2010), 3458-3463.
- [2] Aktas. H., C. agman N., ~ Soft sets and soft groups, *Inform. Sci.*, 177(2007), 2726-2735.
- [3] Ali M.I., Feng F., Liu X., Min W.K., Shabir M., On some new operations in soft set theory, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 57(2009), 1547-1553.
- [4] Atagun A.O., Sezgin A., Soft substructures of rings, fields and modules, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 61(3)(2011), 592-601.
- [5] Babitha K.V., Sunil J.J., Soft set relations and functions, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 60(7)(2010), 1840-1849.

- [6] Cagman N., Enginoglu S., Soft matrix theory and its decision making, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 59(2010), 3308-3314.
- [7] Cagman N., Enginoglu S., Soft set theory and uni-int decision making, *Eur. J. Oper. Res.*, 207(2010), 848-855.
- [8] Cagman N., Çiçek F., Aktas, H., Soft int-groups and its applications to group theory, *Neural Comput. Appl.*, DOI: 10.1007/s00521-011-0752-x.
- [9] Cagman N., Sezgin A., Atagün A.O., Soft uni-groups and its applications to group theory, (submitted).
- [10] Cagman N., Sezgin A., Atagün A.O., α -inclusions and their applications to group theory, (submitted).
- [11] F. Feng, W. Pedrycz, On scalar products and decomposition theorems of fuzzy soft sets, *Journal of Multivalued Logic and Soft Computing*, 2015, 25(1), 45-80.
- [12] F. Feng, J. Cho, W. Pedrycz, H. Fujita, T. Herawan, Soft set based association rule mining, *Knowledge-Based Systems*, 111 (2016), 268-282
- [13] Feng F., Li C., Davvaz B., Ali M.I., Soft sets combined with fuzzy sets and rough sets: a tentative approach, *Soft Comput.*, 14(6)(2010), 899-911.
- [14] Jun Y.B., Soft BCK/BCI-algebras, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 56(2008), 1408 -1413.
- [15] Jun Y.B., Park C.H., Applications of soft sets in ideal theory of BCK/ BCI-algebras, *Inform. Sci.*, 178(2008), 2466-2475.
- [16] Jun Y.B., Lee K.J., Zhan J., Soft p-ideals of soft BCI-algebras, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 58(2009), 2060-2068.
- [17] Jun Y.B., Lee K.J., Park C.H., Soft set theory applied to ideals in d-algebras, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 57(3)(2009), 367-378.
- [18] Kazancı O., Yılmaz S., Yamak S., Soft sets and soft BCH-algebras, *Hacet. J. Math. Stat.*, 39(2)(2010), 205-217.
- [19] Maji P.K., Biswas R., Roy A.R., Soft set theory, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 45(2003), 555-562.
- [20] Maji P.K., Roy A.R., Biswas R., An application of soft sets in a decision making problem, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 44(2002), 1077-1083.
- [21] Majumdar P., Samanta S.K., On soft mappings, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 60 (9)(2010), 2666-2672.
- [22] Molodtsov D., Soft set theory-first results, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 37(1999), 19-31.

- [23] Molodtsov D.A., Leonov V.Yu., Kovkov D.V., Soft sets technique and its application, *Nechetkie Sistemy i Myagkie Vychisleniya*, 1(1)(2006), 8-39.
- [24] Pilz G., *Near-rings*, North Holland Publishing Company, Amsterdam-New York-Oxford, 1983.
- [25] Sezgin A., Atagun A.O., Aygün E., " A note on soft near-rings and idealistic soft near-rings, *Filomat.*, 25(1)(2011), 53-68.
- [26] Sezgin A., Atagun A.O., " On operations of soft sets, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 61(5)(2011), 1457-1467.
- [27] Wendt G., On Zero Divisors in Near-Rings, *Int. J. Algebra*, 3(1)(2009), 21-32.
- [28] Zhan J., Jun Y.B., Soft BL-algebras based on fuzzy sets, *Comput. Math. Appl.*, 59(6)(2010), 2037-2046.
- [29] Zou Y., Xiao Z., Data analysis approaches of soft sets under incomplete information, *Knowl-Based Syst.*, 21(2008), 941-945.
- [30] J. Zhan, B. Yu, V. Fotea, Characterizations of two kinds of hemi rings based on probability spaces, *Soft Comput.*, 20 (2016), 637-648.